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ASSESSING THE UTILITY OF SYNTHETIC DATA: A DENSITY RATIO PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Synthetic data can be a solution to reduce disclosure risks that arise when disseminating research data to the public. However, for the synthetic data to be useful for general inferential purposes, it is paramount that its distribution is similar to the distribution of the observed data. Often, data disseminators consider multiple synthetic data models and make refinements in an iterative fashion. After each adjustment, it is crucial to evaluate whether the quality of the synthetic data has actually improved. Although many methods exist to provide such an evaluation, their results are often incomplete or even misleading. To improve the evaluation strategy for synthetic data, and thereby the quality of synthetic data itself, we propose to use the density ratio estimation framework. Using techniques from this field, we show how an interpretable utility measure can be obtained from the ratio of the observed and synthetic data densities. We show how the density ratio estimation framework bridges the gap between fit-for-purpose and global utility measures, and discuss how it can also be used to evaluate analysis-specific utility. Using empirical examples, we show that density ratio estimation improves on existing (global) utility measures by providing higher statistical power and offering a fine-grained view of discrepancies between the observed and synthetic data. Moreover, we describe several additional advantages of the approach, such as providing a measure of utility on the level of individual synthetic data points, automatic model selection without requiring user specification, and readily available high-dimensional extensions. We conclude that density ratio estimation provides a promising framework in synthetic data generation workflows and present an R-package with functionality to implement the approach.

Introduction

In recent years, the academic interest in synthetic data has exploded. Synthetic data are increasingly being used as a solution to overcome privacy and confidentiality issues that are inherently linked to the dissemination of research data. National statistical institutes and other government agencies have started to disseminate synthetic data to the public while restricting access to the original data to protect sensitive information (e.g., [Abowd, Stinson, and Benedetto 2006](#); [Hawala 2008](#); [Drechsler 2012](#)). At the same time, researchers began to share synthetic versions of their research data to comply with open science standards (e.g., [van de Wiel et al. 2023](#); [Obermeyer et al. 2019](#); [Zettler et al. 2021](#)). Rather than sharing the original research data, a synthetic surrogate is shared to facilitate reviewing of the data processing and analysis pipeline. Additionally, synthetic data is increasingly being used for training machine learning models ([Nikolenko 2021](#)). On a lower level, synthetic data can be used in model testing pipelines (before access to the real data is provided), for data exploration, and for educational purposes.

At its core, the idea of synthetic data is to replace values from the observed data with new values that are generated from a model. In this way, it is possible to generate an entirely new synthetic data set (commonly referred to as the *fully* synthetic data approach; [Rubin 1993](#)), but also to replace just those values that are sensitive or that would yield a high risk of disclosure when released (an approach called *partially* synthetic data; [Little 1993](#)). Both approaches attempt to build a model that incorporates as much of the information in the real data as possible, given a pre-specified privacy risk level that is still deemed acceptable. The models used to generate synthetic data were originally closely related to methods used for multiple imputation of missing data, such as fully conditional specification ([Volker and Vink 2021](#)) or sequential regression ([Nowok, Raab, and Dibben 2016](#)). Recently, significant improvements in generative modelling sparked the scientific interest in synthetic data in the computer science community, leading to novel synthesis methods (e.g., [Patki, Wedge, and Veeramachaneni 2016](#); [Xu et al. 2019](#)). Combined with work on formal privacy guarantees, this resulted in new models that explicitly control the level of privacy risk in synthesis methods ([Jordon, Yoon, and Schaar 2019](#); [Torkzadehmahani, Kairouz, and Paten 2019](#)). Through both methodological advances and practical implementations, data synthesis has evolved into an increasingly popular approach to enhance data dissemination.

Regardless of these developments, the main challenge when generating synthetic data remains to adequately balance the privacy risk with the utility (i.e., quality) of the synthetic data. On the upper limit of this privacy-utility trade-off, the synthesis model captures the information in the observed data so precisely that the real data is exactly reproduced, resulting in the same privacy loss as when disseminating the real data. In statistical terms, the synthesis model is overparameterized to such an extent that there are no degrees of freedom left, and there is thus no randomness involved in the generation of the synthetic values. On the lower limit of the trade-off, synthetic values are generated without borrowing any information from the real data. For example, we could place the value 0 or a random draw from a standard normal distribution for every record and every variable, such that the synthetic data contains only noise. Synthetic data sets sit somewhere between these extremes: they contain some information from the real data, yielding some disclosure risk, but they also resemble the real data to some extent, yielding more than zero utility. Because not all information is captured, the utility of the synthetic data will always be lower than the utility of the real data. The question that naturally arises is where on the privacy-utility continuum the synthetic data is located: how much information is sacrificed, and which aspects of the real data are reproduced in the synthetic data. From the perspective of the data provider, it is important to know how informative the released data is, while the user wants to know whether their analysis can be reliably performed. Additionally, the data provider can use knowledge about the utility to finetune the synthesis model and improve the synthetic data quality.

To evaluate the utility of synthetic data, three classes of utility measures have been distinguished (for a thorough review of these measures, see [Drechsler and Haensch 2023](#)): fit-for-purpose measures, global utility measures, and analysis-specific utility measures. Fit-for-purpose measures are often the first step in assessing the quality of the synthetic data. They typically involve comparing the univariate distributions of the observed and synthetic data (for example using visualization techniques or goodness-of-fit measures). Although these measures provide an initial impression of the quality of the synthesis models used, this picture is by definition limited, because only one or two variables are assessed at the same time. Hence, complex relationships between variables will always be out of scope. Global utility measures build on the fit-for-purpose measures, but attempt to capture the quality of the entire multivariate distribution of the synthetic data relative to the observed data in a single, global, indicator. This can be done using some distance measure (e.g., the Kullback-Leibler divergence; see [Karr et al. 2006](#)), but also by estimating how well a prediction model can distinguish between the observed and synthetic data, using the predicted probabilities (propensity scores; [Rosenbaum and Rubin 1983](#)) as a measure of discrepancy (e.g., the propensity score mean squared error, $pMSE$; [Woo et al. 2009](#); [Snok et al. 2018](#)). While global utility measures paint a

rather complete picture, and provide information over the entire range of the data, they tend to be too general. That is, global utility measures can be so broad that important discrepancies between the real and synthetic are missed, and a synthetic data set with high global utility might still yield analyses with results that are far from the results from real data analyses (see Drechsler 2022). Lastly, the analysis-specific utility measures quantify to what extent analyses performed on the synthetic data align with the same analyses on the observed data. These measures can, for example, evaluate how similar the coefficients of a regression model are (e.g., using the confidence interval overlap; Karr et al. 2006), or whether prediction models trained on the synthetic and observed data perform comparably in terms of evaluation metrics. However, analysis-specific utility generally does not carry over: high specific utility for one analysis does not at all imply high utility for another analysis. Since data providers typically do not know which analyses will be performed with the synthetic data, it is impossible to provide analysis-specific utility measures for all potentially relevant analyses (see also Drechsler 2022).

In this paper, we propose to use the framework of density ratio estimation (Sugiyama, Suzuki, and Kanamori 2012a) to place all above measures under a common umbrella. We show empirically that this approach performs at least as well as various existing utility measures, while providing a more fine-grained view of the misfit of the synthetic data. Moreover, the typically non-parametric nature of density ratio estimation in combination with automatic model selection mitigates the burden around model specification of existing utility measures as the $pMSE$. In short, density ratio estimation compares the (multivariate) distributions of two data sets (e.g., two different samples or groups) by directly estimating the ratio of their densities. Crucially, this method does not estimate the densities of the observed and synthetic data separately, subsequently taking their ratio, but estimates the density ratio directly, which has been shown to yield better performance (e.g., Kanamori, Hido, and Sugiyama 2009). The idea is that if two data sets are drawn from the same data-generating mechanism, the sampled data should be similar, and the ratio of their densities should be close to one over the entire multivariate space. This approach readily extends from univariate to bivariate and multivariate densities, and thus bridges the gap between fit-for-purpose and global utility measures. Moreover, we briefly discuss how density ratio estimation can be used to compare the distributions of parameters of observed and synthetic data, to incorporate analysis-specific utility measures as well. Hence, we show that it is a versatile approach that is useful in the entire domain of data utility.

Also from the privacy-side several promising advances have been made to quantify the amount of information leakage through the synthetic data. Important work has been done to build formal privacy guarantees into the synthesis models through differential privacy (Dwork 2006). In addition to these privacy-by-design mechanisms, some measures exist to quantify privacy loss of synthetic data after generation (e.g., McClure and Reiter 2016; Reiter and Mitra 2009; Hu 2019). However, the practical applicability of these measures depends on whether the data is fully or partially synthetic, and especially in case of the former, the practical applicability of these measures is often limited (for an extensive discussion of these issues, see Drechsler and Haensch 2023). More research on measures to evaluate disclosure risks in synthetic data is thus certainly needed, but in this paper we focus exclusively on measuring utility.

In what follows, we describe the density ratio estimation framework by summarizing some of the work in this area, and show how it provides a useful framework for measuring utility of synthetic data. Subsequently, we illustrate how the method can be used in practice by providing multiple examples, and empirically compare its performance to existing utility measures. Lastly, we discuss how density ratio estimation relates to existing utility measures, describe current shortcomings of the approach and relate these shortcomings to avenues for future work.

Density ratio estimation

The density ratio estimation framework was originally developed in the machine learning community for the comparison of two probability distributions (for an overview, see Sugiyama, Suzuki, and Kanamori 2012a). The framework has been shown to be applicable to prediction (Sugiyama et al. 2010; Sugiyama 2010), outlier detection (Hido et al. 2008), change-point detection in time-series (Liu et al. 2013), importance weighting under domain adaptation (i.e., sample selection bias; Kanamori, Hido, and Sugiyama 2009), and, importantly, two-sample homogeneity tests (Sugiyama, Suzuki, et al. 2011). The general idea of density ratio estimation is depicted in Figure 1, and boils down to comparing two distributions by modelling the density ratio $r(\mathbf{x})$ between the probability distributions of the numerator samples, taken from the synthetic data distribution, $p_{syn}(\mathbf{x})$, and the denominator samples, taken from the observed data distribution, $p_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$, such that

$$r(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{p_{syn}(\mathbf{x})}{p_{obs}(\mathbf{x})}. \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 1. Example of the density ratio of two normal distributions with different means and variances (i.e., $N(0, 1)$ and $N(1, 2)$). Note that the density ratio is itself not a proper density.

This specification has the intuitive interpretation that if the density ratio is large, too many synthetic values will be generated in that region, whereas if the density ratio is small, there will be too few synthetic observations, both relative to the observed data. An intuitive approach to estimating $r(\mathbf{x})$ from samples of $p_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$ and $p_{syn}(\mathbf{x})$ would be to estimate the observed and synthetic data density separately, for example using kernel density estimation (Scott 1992), and subsequently compute the ratio of these estimated densities. However, density estimation is one of the hardest tasks in statistical learning, unavoidably leading to estimation errors for both densities. When subsequently taking the ratio of the estimated densities, the estimation errors might be magnified, resulting in a poorer estimate of the density ratio than necessary as compared to direct estimation. An alternative is to specify and estimate a model directly for the ratio without first estimating the separate densities. Extensive simulations on a wide variety of tasks showed that this approach typically outperforms density ratio estimation through naive kernel density estimation, especially when the dimensionality of the data increases (e.g., Kanamori, Suzuki, and Sugiyama 2012; Hido et al. 2008; Kanamori, Hido, and Sugiyama 2009).

Over the past years, several methods for direct density ratio estimation have been developed. Typically, these methods aim to minimize some discrepancy $\mathcal{D}(r(\mathbf{x}), \hat{r}(\mathbf{x}))$ between the true density ratio and some density ratio model. One commonly used discrepancy measure is the following squared error

$$\mathcal{S}_0(r(\mathbf{x}), \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})) = \frac{1}{2} \int (\hat{r}(\mathbf{x}) - r(\mathbf{x}))^2 p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (2)$$

which can be considered as the expected discrepancy between the two functions over the density of the observed data. One could also use other discrepancy measures, such as the binary or unnormalized Kullback-Leibler divergence or Basu’s power divergence (which are all members of the family of Bregman divergences; for a detailed discussion, see Sugiyama, Suzuki, and Kanamori 2012b). It is convenient to model the density ratio with a linear model, such that

$$\hat{r}(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x})\boldsymbol{\theta}, \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x})$ is a non-negative basis function vector that transforms the data from a p -dimensional to a b -dimensional space, and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a b -dimensional parameter vector. Although the model is linear in its parameters, the density ratio itself is a non-linear function of the data if $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x})$ is a non-linear transformation of the data, which it typically is.

To illustrate the idea of density ratio estimation, we briefly review one method from the field: unconstrained least squares importance fitting (Kanamori, Hido, and Sugiyama 2009), which will also be used in our illustrations in the upcoming section. The authors show that the squared error can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_0(r(\mathbf{x}), \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})) &= \frac{1}{2} \int \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} - \int \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})r(\mathbf{x})p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \int r(\mathbf{x})^2 p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} - \int \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})p_{syn}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} + C, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $r(\mathbf{x})$ in the second term on the first line is rewritten in terms of the ratio of $p_{syn}(\mathbf{x})$ over $p_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$. After dropping the irrelevant (with respect to the data) constant C , and substituting the density ratio model as defined in Equation 3, we have

$$\mathcal{S}(r(\mathbf{x}), \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})) = \frac{1}{2} \int \boldsymbol{\theta}' \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x})' \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}) \boldsymbol{\theta} p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} - \int \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}) \boldsymbol{\theta} p_{syn}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (5)$$

as the objective function. The integrals in Equation 5 are typically not available, but can be replaced by empirical averages, such that

$$\hat{\mathcal{S}}(r(\mathbf{x}), \hat{r}(\mathbf{x})) = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\theta}' \left(\frac{1}{n_{obs}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs})' \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs}) \right) \boldsymbol{\theta} - \left(\frac{1}{n_{syn}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{syn})' \mathbf{1}_{n_{syn}} \right) \boldsymbol{\theta}. \quad (6)$$

It follows directly that the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ can be estimated as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \left(\frac{1}{n_{obs}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs})' \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs}) \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{n_{syn}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{syn})' \mathbf{1}_{n_{syn}} \right), \quad (7)$$

which shows the least-squares nature of the problem. Because one would expect the density ratio to be non-negative, a non-negativity constraint for $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ can be added to the optimization problem, which would yield a convex quadratic optimization problem that can be solved with dedicated software. However, ignoring the non-negativity constraint has the advantage that Equation 6 has an analytical expression, which is numerically stable and computationally very efficient. The corresponding downside of having negative estimated density ratio values can be remedied by setting negative values in $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ to 0.

From here, we are left with two remaining tasks. First, one typically wants to add a regularization parameter λ to the objective function to prevent overfitting and ensure positive-definiteness. In the unconstrained realm, a ridge penalty $(\lambda/2)\boldsymbol{\theta}'\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is typically added to the optimization problem in Equation 6. Adding this to the solution in Equation 7 yields

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \left(\frac{1}{n_{obs}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs})' \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{obs}) + \lambda \mathbf{I}_b \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{n_{syn}} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}_{syn})' \mathbf{1}_{n_{syn}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{I}_b denotes a $b \times b$ identity matrix. The regularization parameter λ can be chosen via cross-validation. Conveniently, the *leave-one-out cross-validation* score can also be computed analytically when using unconstrained least-squares importance fitting (see Section 3.4 in Kanamori, Hido, and Sugiyama 2009). Second, we need to specify the basis functions used in the density ratio model. A common choice is to use a Gaussian kernel, which quantifies the similarity between observations as

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{c}) = \exp \left(- \frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\|^2}{2\sigma^2} \right), \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{c} denotes the Gaussian centers and σ controls the kernel width. The bandwidth parameter σ can also be selected using cross-validation. Typically a subset of the numerator samples are chosen as the Gaussian centers, because the density ratio tends to take large values at locations where the numerator density has more mass than the denominator density. To estimate the density ratio accurately, we may use many kernels where the density ratio is expected to be large, whereas having few kernels might suffice in the locations where the density ratio is small. Hence, we place many kernels where the synthetic data density is large, by taking a sample of the synthetic records as Gaussian centers, with the number of samples n_c dependent on the computational resources available (but typically $\min(100, n_{syn}) \leq n_c \leq \min(1000, n_{syn})$).

After estimating the density ratio, one can assess whether the numerator and denominator densities differ significantly via a permutation test. To this end, Sugiyama, Suzuki, et al. (2011) propose a two-sample test that quantifies the discrepancy between the numerator (synthetic) and denominator (observed) samples through the density ratio, using the Pearson divergence $\mathcal{P}(p_{syn}(\mathbf{x}), p_{obs}(\mathbf{x}))$ as a test statistic:

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}(p_{syn}(\mathbf{x}), p_{obs}(\mathbf{x})) = \frac{1}{2n_{syn}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{syn}} \hat{r}(\mathbf{x}_{syn}^{(i)}) - \frac{1}{n_{obs}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{obs}} \hat{r}(\mathbf{x}_{obs}^{(j)}) + \frac{1}{2}. \quad (10)$$

Intuitively, this discrepancy captures how different the synthetic data is from the observed data by measuring the distance from the density ratio at the observed data points to the density ratio at the synthetic data points. As we show in our empirical examples, this statistic is difficult to interpret in an absolute sense. However, we show that it is useful as a relative measure of fit of the different synthetic data sets. Additionally, the value of the test statistic can be used to construct a hypothesis test for the lack of fit of the synthetic data using a permutation test. An empirical p -value can then be calculated as the proportion of test statistics under the null model that are greater than the observed test statistic. In this way, it can be assessed whether the synthetic data model is misspecified, by comparing the observed value to what can be expected under a correctly specified synthesis model.

Density ratio estimation as a utility measure: Simulated and empirical examples

In this section, we illustrate density ratio estimation using unconstrained least-squares importance fitting. In a small simulation, we show that the method gives reasonable results when the goal is to estimate a density ratio in several parametric examples. Subsequently, we use these examples to show how the results of density ratio estimation can be used as a measure of utility, and we describe how a lack of fit of the synthesis model can be inferred from the density ratio. Starting with univariate examples, we compare the density ratio two-sample test with existing goodness-of-fit measures (the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the $pMSE$). As a final illustration, we build upon the work by Drechsler (2022), and showcase how density ratio estimation improves upon utility assessment through the $pMSE$ in a multivariate example. All analyses were conducted in R (Version 4.3.0; R Core Team 2023), and the code is available on [GitHub](#). The software used to perform density ratio estimation is implemented in an R-package called `densityratio` (Volker 2023).

Density ratio estimation in simulated univariate examples

To provide an intuition about the performance of unconstrained least-squares importance fitting, we apply it to a simplified example of a typical situation in the synthetic data field. When creating synthetic data, we often have a complex, usually unknown, data distribution that we want to approximate with a model. We generally lack information to correctly model real-world phenomena, and even if we would have sufficient information, some important factors might be missing from the data, or the model might be so complex that it is unfeasible to actually simulate data from it. For the sake of illustrational clarity, we generate univariate data according to four true data-generating mechanisms:

1. Laplace($\mu = 1, b = 1$)
2. Log-normal($\mu_{\log} = \log\{\mu^2/\sqrt{\mu^2 + \sigma_x^2}\}, \sigma_{\log}^2 = \log\{1 + \sigma_x^2/\mu^2\}$), with $\mu = 1$ and $\sigma_x^2 = 2$
3. Location-scale t -distribution $lst(\mu = 1, \tau^2 = 1, \nu = 4)$
4. Normal($\mu = 1, \sigma_x^2 = 2$)

Note that these four distributions all have the same population mean $\mu = 1$ and the same population variance $\sigma_x^2 = 2$. From each distribution, we generate 200 data sets of size $n_{obs} = 250$. For all scenarios, we approximate the true data-generating mechanism by drawing 200 data sets of size $n_{syn} = 250$ from a normal distribution (Normal($\mu = 1, \sigma_x^2 = 2$)), such that we accurately model the mean and variance of each true data-generating distribution (see also Figure 2 for a graphical depiction of the true and synthetic data densities). Note that in the fourth scenario, we thus model the true data-generating distribution correctly, which is included to get some intuition on how density ratio estimation performs when we specify the synthesis model correctly. All density ratios were estimated with the exact same model specifications: we used 100 observations from the synthetic data as Gaussian centers and performed cross-validation over 10 values of the Gaussian kernel width σ and 10 values of the regularization parameter λ .

Figure 3 shows how the estimated density ratios for the 200 simulated datasets in each scenario (the blue lines in each subfigure) compared to the true density ratios (the black lines). In each of the four figures, the estimated density ratios follow the general trend of the true density ratios. In the top-left plot, showing the ratio of the normal distribution over the Laplace distribution, the density ratio decreases at the sides, then increases when moving towards the center, but decreases again close to the center. The same can be observed in the bottom-left plot, which shows the normal distribution over the lst -distribution. In the top right panel, the estimated density ratios are typically large for negative values, very close to zero (or even negative) around the peak of the log-normal distribution, and subsequently increasing and later on decreasing again. In the bottom right panel, where both distributions are identical, the majority of the estimated density ratios are very flat, tending towards zero to some extent at the edges of the figure where only few data points are located. Moreover, all figures show some highly variable estimated density ratios due to modest overfitting regardless of the cross-validation scheme, whereas the normal versus log-normal figure shows many highly variable estimates outside of the center of the figure, due to the fact that either the synthetic or the observed data has only few cases in these regions. Normally, the stability of the estimates increases with the sample size. Figure 3 also shows one of the main advantages of density ratio estimation as a utility measure, in the sense that it provides a quantification of the fit for every data point. At those locations where the estimated density ratio takes large values, there are too many synthetic observations compared to what should be expected based on the observed data, whereas at the points where the density ratio is close to zero, there are too few synthetic observations relative to the observed data. Likewise, a high density ratio value for a synthetic record indicates that this point deviates from what would be typical under the observed data-generating mechanism.

FIGURE 2. True and synthetic data densities for the examples considered (Laplace, Log-normal, t and Normal), all distributions have mean $\mu = 1$ and variance $\sigma_x^2 = 2$. Note that the true and synthetic data density in the bottom right plot are completely overlapping.

As it is hard to infer from visualizations whether the misfit could arise from chance alone, or whether the synthetic data model is misspecified, we formally evaluate the fit of the synthetic data by performing statistical inference using the Pearson divergence as a measure of discrepancy (see Equation 10). To explore the properties of the corresponding permutation test, we compare it in terms of power and Type I error rate with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and with a $pMSE$ -based test, obtained by performing a permutation test and assessing the proportion of times the permuted $pMSE$ s are larger than the observed $pMSE$ (Snoké et al. 2018). The $pMSE$ s are calculated by using the `utility.tab()` function with default settings from the R-package `synthpop` (Nowok, Raab, and Dibben 2016). Table 1 shows that in terms of evaluating the misfit of the synthetic data, the density ratio-based test has statistical power similar to the $pMSE$ -based test. That is, when the synthetic data model differs from the observed data-generating mechanism, the density ratio-based test and the $pMSE$ -based test indicate significant misfit in approximately 60% of the simulations for the Laplace data, 100% for the log-normal data and 50% for the location-scale t -distributed data. Both methods achieve considerably higher power than the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. When the synthesis model is correctly specified, all three methods achieve a nominal Type I error rate close to 0.05.

TABLE 1. Proportion of significant tests for the fit of the synthetic data.

Data	Density ratio	Kolmogorov-Smirnov	$pMSE$
Laplace	0.620	0.375	0.610
Log-normal	1.000	1.000	1.000
t	0.495	0.235	0.495
Normal	0.050	0.045	0.040

FIGURE 3. Estimated density ratios by unconstrained least-squares importance fitting in four univariate examples: A Laplace distribution, a log-normal distribution, a t -distribution and a normal distribution, all approximated by a normal distribution with the same mean and variance as the original distributions.

Density ratio estimation for synthetic Current Population Survey data

To evaluate the properties of density ratio estimation in a real-life example, we repeat Drechsler’s (2022) illustration of the $pMSE$ as a fit-for-purpose and global utility measure with a subset of the March 2000 U.S. Current Population Survey, but now using density ratio estimation. Notably, we use the exact same (default) density ratio model specifications as in the previous simulations, both for evaluating the utility of the variables separately and over the synthetic data sets as a whole. We use exactly the same data as Drechsler (2022), that is, the variables *Sex*, *Race*, *Marital Status*, *Highest attained education level*, *Age*, *Social security payments*, *Household property taxes* and *Household income*, measured on $n = 5000$ individuals (descriptive statistics are provided in Table 2 and a graphical depiction of the numeric variables is shown in Figure 6, both in Appendix A). Note that the continuous variables are typically non-normal, while the variables *Household property taxes* and *Social security payments* in addition have a point-mass at zero. Data synthesis is done using the R-package *synthpop* (Nowok, Raab, and Dibben 2016), using the same synthesis strategies as used in Drechsler (2022). We thus refer to this paper for details about the synthesis strategies, and only briefly describe the synthesis models here. Three of the synthetic data sets are created using parametric models: *Sex* and *Race* are synthesized with logistic regression models, *Marital status* and *Highest attained education* are synthesized using multinomial regression, and all continuous variables are synthesized using a linear model. The parametric synthesis models build up in complexity in how they model the continuous variables in the following way: the first model (labelled *naive*) does not take the distributions of the variables into account, and models the variables on the original scale; the second model (called *transformed*) transforms the variables by taking their cubic root and subsequently applies a linear model to the transformed variables; the third model (labelled *semi-continuous*) also transforms all variables to the cubic root scale, but in addition separately models the point mass at zero for the variables *Household property taxes* and *Social security payments* separately, after which a linear model is used for the non-zero values. The non-parametric synthesis model applies classification and regression trees (CART) to all variables, augmented by smoothing through kernel density estimation in the terminal nodes. For all strategies, $m = 5$ synthetic data sets are generated, and the utility is assessed by averaging the Pearson divergence over those sets. As noted

FIGURE 4. Real and synthetic data distributions for the variables age, household income (income), household property taxes (tax) and social security payments (social security) on a cubic root scale (using $f(x) = \text{sign}(x)|x|^{1/3}$).

by Drechsler (2022), based on the sequential refinements of the parametric synthesis models, one would expect the utility to improve with every parametric model, leaving open how the CART models compare to the parametric models.

Figure 4 shows how the increasing complexity of the synthesis models leads to increasingly realistic synthetic data distributions (all variables are plotted on a cubic root scale using $f(x) = \text{sign}(x)|x|^{1/3}$ to also allow for negative values). It is evident that the *naive* synthesis strategy does a poor job for all variables except *Age*, whereas the *transformed* strategy does a poor job for *Tax* and *Social security*. The *semi-continuous* strategy seems to fit well for all variables, similarly to the data created with CART, although the latter method preserves the non-normality of the non-zero values in *Social security* slightly better. The insights from visual inspection are entirely corroborated by the relative Pearson divergences as given by density ratio estimation (see Figure 5). For all variables, the *naive* synthesis method performs worst. Typically, the *transformed* synthesis improves the synthetic data to some extent, although the difference is relatively small for *Age*, because here the *naive* synthesis strategy already performed reasonable. For both *Age* and *Income*, the *transformed* strategy performs similarly to both the *semi-continuous* and the CART strategies, because for these variables there is no point-mass to model separately. For the variables where a point-mass is modeled separately (e.g., *Social security* and *Tax*), the *semi-continuous* approach clearly outperforms the *transformed* strategy. Lastly, CART outperforms the *naive* and *transformed* strategies, and performs highly similar to the *semi-continuous* approach.

When modelling the density ratio over all variables in the data simultaneously (including the categorical variables, for simplicity recoded as numeric variables to be included in density ratio estimation), we see the same picture emerging.

FIGURE 5. Pearson divergence estimates after different synthesis strategies for the separate variables and the synthetic data sets as a whole.

Figure 5 shows the stepwise improvements in utility when refining the synthesis models. *Naïve* synthesis clearly performs worst, followed by the *transformed* strategy. Both strategies are outperformed by the *semi-continuous* approach, which performs more or less on par with CART. These results compare favorably with utility assessment through the $pMSE$ as reported in Drechsler (2022). The evaluation of utility through the $pMSE$ shows no improvement when going from *naïve* to *transformed* synthesis, whereas some $pMSE$ models qualified the *naïve* approach as better than the *transformed* approach. The improvement from the first two strategies to *semi-continuous* and CART was picked up by most $pMSE$ models. Hence, the utility assigned by density ratio estimation was more in line with the refinements to the synthesis models than the utility scores that were obtained with the $pMSE$.

Discussion

When creating synthetic data with the goal of private data release, it is crucial to evaluate its quality. This allows the data provider to decide whether the synthetic data is useful for the purposes of the release or requires further refinements, and to inform the data user about the analyses that can be reliably conducted. In this paper, we showed that density ratio estimation provides a promising framework to evaluate the utility of synthetic data and we implemented the approach in the R-package `densityratio` (Volker 2023). In a small simulation, we showed that for sample sizes as small as 250 observations, it was possible to obtain a rather accurate estimate of the true density ratio. Moreover, in terms of statistical power, density ratio estimation performed on par with the $pMSE$ and outperforms the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test in the univariate comparisons considered. When evaluating density ratio estimation on multiple synthetic versions of a real-world data set, we showed that the method was able to pick up all improvements in the synthesis models made, in contrast to the $pMSE$ (as shown by Drechsler 2022). Moreover, whereas Drechsler (2022) showed that quantification of the utility through the $pMSE$ was highly dependent on the propensity score model, density ratio estimation possesses automatic model selection in terms of its hyperparameters, and thus requires almost no user-specification. We emphasize that we used the same default settings for our simulations and for modelling all individual variables and the entire data sets in our empirical example, regardless of the varying scales of the variables and other variable-specific peculiarities, such as point masses and non-normality.

Although this paper focused on various comparisons, we note that there are many connections between density ratio estimation and existing utility measures. For example, the $pMSE$ can be considered as an instance of density ratio

estimation, in which the propensity scores are used to model the density ratio. Specifically, the propensity scores can be transformed into the posterior odds of any record belonging to the synthetic data versus the observed data, which yields an estimate of the density ratio. Additionally, Sugiyama, Suzuki, and Kanamori (2012a) show that density ratio estimation can be regarded as divergence estimation between the numerator and denominator density. As such, the framework also encompasses estimation of, for example, the Kullback-Leibler divergence, proposed as utility measure by Karr et al. (2006). Lastly, density ratio estimation can be seen as an extension of the “ratio of estimates” utility measure (Taub, Elliot, and Sakshaug 2020), which is defined for categorical data as the ratio of observed and synthetic frequencies (scaled to be between 0 and 1 by putting the largest count in the denominator), to continuous data. As such, the density ratio framework encapsulates various measures to evaluate the utility of synthetic data.

Expanding upon the appealing properties discussed in this paper, we foresee three additional advantages of the density ratio framework. **(1) Utility on the level of individual data points.** The density ratio is estimated over the entire (multivariate) space of the data, and these estimates can be used to quantify the deviation of every synthetic data point with respect to the observed data. These values can help to identify sub-spaces that are poorly reproduced in the synthetic data, but they might also yield additional benefits. On a low level, these values might be used to discard observations that are considered as being too far from the observed data to be realistic, or resample observations that are typical in the observed data but occur infrequently in the synthetic data. On a higher level, one could potentially use density ratio values to reweigh analyses with synthetic data to bring the results closer to the real data. Future research should evaluate the merits of this approach, but also potential privacy risks of disseminating such weights. **(2) Density ratios for specific utility.** Another potential benefit is that the use of the method is not necessarily restricted to the level of the data at hand. Density ratio estimation could give rise to analysis-specific utility measures by applying the framework on the posterior distributions of parameters (or an approximation hereof). That is, if the distribution of the parameters of the analysis model can be approximated, for example by a multivariate normal distribution, or when samples from the parameter distribution are available, it is possible to either analytically calculate the density ratio, or estimate it using the techniques described above. The resulting density ratio can then again be used to quantify how similar the distributions are. **(3) Extensions to high-dimensional data.** When the number of variables grows large relative to the number of observations, direct density ratio estimation through unconstrained least-squares importance fitting might become inaccurate. However, the density ratio estimation framework possesses readily available extensions that include dimension reduction as part of the estimation process, which yields the advantage of simultaneously optimizing the density ratio solution with the dimension-reduced subspace of the data (Sugiyama, Yamada, et al. 2011).

Finally, let us remark that there are several open questions that need to be addressed before density ratio estimation can be fully incorporated in synthetic data evaluation pipelines. First, methodological research should investigate how to deal with categorical variables. In the density ratio estimation framework, the focus has almost exclusively been on numeric data, whereas in practical situations, categorical data is all too common. In this paper, we dealt with the issue by simply transforming the categorical variables into numeric variables, but other techniques might yield more accurate results. To name three other strategies, one could transform the categorical variables into dummy variables, use a different distance metric that allows for categorical data when specifying the kernel, or assume an underlying continuous latent space, and model the categorical variables on this space. Second, which default settings to use in density ratio estimation is still an open question. Although we showed that our default settings performed reasonably, most choices lack a strong theoretical justification. Potentially, the utility of synthetic data can be evaluated much more accurately by, for example, choosing a different kernel, choosing the centers in the Gaussian kernel in a different way, or using a broader range of bandwidth and regularization parameters. Lastly, it must be evaluated what information from density ratio estimation can be released to the public without incurring severe privacy risks. Presumably, releasing the Pearson divergence, potentially augmented with a p -value to indicate the lack of fit of the synthetic data, will yield only little additional privacy risk. However, releasing visualizations of the estimated density ratio or the estimated density ratio values themselves might cause unacceptable threats, especially for observations in the tails of the distribution. Future research can make efforts to privatize the output from density ratio estimation, or at least investigate what risks are related to releasing the output of the estimation process. With these promising avenues for extensions in mind, we conclude that the density ratio estimation framework provides a viable and intuitive alternative to existing utility measures that can enhance synthetic data workflows.

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Appendix A - Description of the CPS data

TABLE 2. Descriptive statistics of the considered subset of observations and variables in the March 2000 U.S. Current Population Survey.

	Overall
	(N=5000)
Sex	
Male	2823 (56.5%)
Female	2177 (43.5%)
Race	
White	4272 (85.4%)
Non-white	728 (14.6%)
Marital status	
Married	2698 (54.0%)
Separated	564 (11.3%)
Widowed	692 (13.8%)
Single	145 (2.9%)
Widowed or divorced	901 (18.0%)
Highest attained education level	
No High School Diploma	815 (16.3%)
High School Diploma	1610 (32.2%)
Associate or bachelor's degree	2121 (42.4%)
Master's degree or higher	454 (9.1%)
Age	
Mean (SD)	48.2 (16.8)
Median [Min, Max]	46.0 [15.0, 90.0]
Social security payments	
Mean (SD)	2180 (4680)
Median [Min, Max]	0 [0, 50000]
Household property taxes	
Mean (SD)	1020 (2500)
Median [Min, Max]	450 [0, 98400]
Household income	
Mean (SD)	54000 (50400)
Median [Min, Max]	40700 [1.00, 583000]

FIGURE 6. Histograms of the considered subset of observations and continuous variables in the March 2000 U.S. Current Population Survey.